

STROBE Statement—Checklist of items that should be included in reports of *cross-sectional studies*

	Item No	Recommendation	Section/ line
Title and abstract	1	(a) Indicate the study’s design with a commonly used term in the title or the abstract	yes
		(b) Provide in the abstract an informative and balanced summary of what was done and what was found	yes
Introduction			
Background/rationale	2	Explain the scientific background and rationale for the investigation being reported	yes
Objectives	3	State specific objectives, including any prespecified hypotheses	sec.1, line 104-105
Methods			
Study design	4	Present key elements of study design early in the paper	sec. 2.1, line 108
Setting	5	Describe the setting, locations, and relevant dates, including periods of recruitment, exposure, follow-up, and data collection	sec. 2.1, line 109-110, sec 2.2, line 130-134
Participants	6	(a) Give the eligibility criteria, and the sources and methods of selection of participants	sec. 2.1, line 111-123
Variables	7	Clearly define all outcomes, exposures, predictors, potential confounders, and effect modifiers. Give diagnostic criteria, if applicable	sec. 2.2, line 130-132
Data sources/ measurement	8*	For each variable of interest, give sources of data and details of methods of assessment (measurement). Describe comparability of assessment methods if there is more than one group	sec. 2.2, line 133-156
Bias	9	Describe any efforts to address potential sources of bias	sec. 2.2, line 136-137
Study size	10	Explain how the study size was arrived at	sec. 2.1, line 109-110, 129-130
Quantitative variables	11	Explain how quantitative variables were handled in the analyses. If applicable, describe which groupings were chosen and why	sec. 2.2, line 143-160, 164-167
Statistical methods	12	(a) Describe all statistical methods, including those used to control for confounding	sec. 2.3, line 222-229
		(b) Describe any methods used to examine subgroups and interactions	sec. 2.3, line 226-227
		(c) Explain how missing data were addressed	sec. 2.3, line 229
		(d) If applicable, describe analytical methods taking account of sampling strategy	not applicable We used Slovin's formula to determine the sample size
		(e) Describe any sensitivity analyses	sec. 2.3, line 227-229
Results			

Participants	13*	(a) Report numbers of individuals at each stage of study—eg numbers potentially eligible, examined for eligibility, confirmed eligible, included in the study, completing follow-up, and analysed	sec. 3, line 233-234
		(b) Give reasons for non-participation at each stage	not applicable
		(c) Consider use of a flow diagram	not applicable
Descriptive data	14*	(a) Give characteristics of study participants (eg demographic, clinical, social) and information on exposures and potential confounders	sec. 3, line 235-237
		(b) Indicate number of participants with missing data for each variable of interest	not applicable
Outcome data	15*	Report numbers of outcome events or summary measures	sec. 3, line 244-250
Main results	16	(a) Give unadjusted estimates and, if applicable, confounder-adjusted estimates and their precision (eg, 95% confidence interval). Make clear which confounders were adjusted for and why they were included	not applicable
		(b) Report category boundaries when continuous variables were categorized	not applicable
		(c) If relevant, consider translating estimates of relative risk into absolute risk for a meaningful time period	not applicable
Other analyses	17	Report other analyses done—eg analyses of subgroups and interactions, and sensitivity analyses	sec. 3, line 254-258
Discussion			
Key results	18	Summarise key results with reference to study objectives	sec. 4.1, line 261-163; sec. 4.2, line 300-302
Limitations	19	Discuss limitations of the study, taking into account sources of potential bias or imprecision. Discuss both direction and magnitude of any potential bias	sec. 4, line 380-393
Interpretation	20	Give a cautious overall interpretation of results considering objectives, limitations, multiplicity of analyses, results from similar studies, and other relevant evidence	sec. 4.1, line 277-282, line 294-297, sec. 4.2, line 332-337
Generalisability	21	Discuss the generalisability (external validity) of the study results	sec. 4, line 374-379, sec. 5, line 397-405
Other information			
Funding	22	Give the source of funding and the role of the funders for the present study and, if applicable, for the original study on which the present article is based	sec. 8, line 418-421

*Give information separately for exposed and unexposed groups.

Note: An Explanation and Elaboration article discusses each checklist item and gives methodological background and published examples of transparent reporting. The STROBE checklist is best used in conjunction with this article (freely

available on the Web sites of PLoS Medicine at <http://www.plosmedicine.org/>, Annals of Internal Medicine at <http://www.annals.org/>, and Epidemiology at <http://www.epidem.com/>). Information on the STROBE Initiative is available at www.strobe-statement.org.